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“MY LIFE, MY LIVING”

In my life, it is vital for me to know and understand how to live, how to survive and how to deal with a happy living. I should be accountable and responsible enough every time I decide everything and make decisions about life. As John T. Adams stated the that there are two things about education of life, that is to say, *first*, how to live and *second* how to make a living. But the question is how am I going to deal with it? On the first phrase, "it should let me know how to live". In this, I should know carefully what are the necessities that I need in order for me to live. I should think critically what are the things that would give benefits for me and to keep me happy and healthy. And the second phrase is that "how to make a living". How am I going to spend and use carefully the vital things I have-as necessities? I shall simply not waste what I have and what are the excess. I shall know how to manage and I need to be responsible enough to save what are needed to be saved. I shall not waste everything that are excess even if it is only cost for a cents. I shall then learn to value everything that I received and that will come in my life.

In this way, I can have a happy and healthy living. The same holds true with the short speech and words of the former CEO of Coca Cola, Bryan Dyson, who once said, "*value has a value only if its value is valued.*" This simply and elegantly means the importance of living a valuable life, i.e., to say, how to value life and make a valuable living of happiness in this techno-driven world. That is why, the ancient philosopher, Aristotle advocates the concept of "*eudaimonia*" (the highest good which is **happiness**) as the penultimate goal of one's life. He persuaded and concluded in his book, Nichomachean Ethics, that the virtuous man is the rational individual or human being who is truly flourishing, satisfying and delighting in every life's way of *eudaimonia* (happiness).

John T. Adams, CEO Bryan Dyson and the philosopher Aristotle basically want us to know that every man should know the idea on how to live and how to make a living not in a perfect way because no one lives in that but in a better (healthy and happy) way. And by knowing this we can experience happiness, a healthy and a better living. With all due respect to their thoughts, they would like us (you & I) to advocate that man should be a steward creation (*imago Dei*) and be responsible and accountable of knowing how to deal with living.

This might not be my personal experiences but this is what I saw on the movie Squid Game. A man is full of debt and he didn't know how to pay it all. He drives into smuggling and cannot even support his daughter. Until a man recruited him to join a game wherein to win an ample of money. And he goes with it not knowing what is the game all about. Upon entering the venue he met new set of friends. The game started and whoever get lose the game will get eliminated and the worst part is they will be killed. And if there is a person who dies, the prize money will increase and that makes them eager to get the money and what happened is

that there is betrayal happened and killings between the players. If I am not mistaken the game is composed of 5 games. And only one man would remain and win and go home the price.

They say, "*walay tawong ma preso ug utang*" and that phrase is actually a fact. There is no person who got into jail because of the absence or the delay of compensating a debt. And the melancholic reality is that we can't live without money. Living without money is dull. Money makes us happy, healthy and alive. But without any proper management it will make our life miserable. That is why some commit mistakes and violent actions just for money. As what I have had seen on the movie, money will make you betray your friends for your own good and life with big debt is dark as a black.

On the movie, there were many people who died and there is no one who we can blame on what happen. Because they are not force to join the game and it's their choice to join in. Our life is similar to the movie we can't live without money and we can't blame no one for what we are and what we are living today. We are the author, facilitator, organizer, master, designer and driver of our journey, so we should take and choose a good way so that we can go to our destination safely, happy and without regrets. So we should know how to live with integrity and be responsible and accountable enough on dealing the challenges in life and be strong enough to shoulder the problems we are carrying. There is no one to blame of what we are now so better choose to live with peace of mind, healthy and a happy life. Yes, money is a big part of our life. It maybe the reason to make our life better but this also makes our living miserable. So, we better choose good living or even a simple life (in the words of Bo Sanchez: "*stay simple, live within the means, engage yourself to business, save and invest!*") and live with our loved ones because it brought us joy and priceless love.

On a personal note, as I embark on the penultimate round of my race to my goals, I have set my sights on my goal and I am willing to do all with all my strength (*love and do whatever I will in life*) by taking the single step to reach out to them. I have been trying to understand the true meaning of entrepreneurship (marketing management is just one part the many parts!) the moment I started to run a motorcycle parts business in our place at the same time finishing my MBA-HRM at La Consolacion College- Bacolod.

Learning new trends and strategies about DM-HRM, teaching with my students (with the different fields: philosophy, history, sociology, business, etc.) managing my business and my people (@ **De Martz Motor Parts**), and weighing on my experience amidst this COVID 19 pandemic, I can identify clearly in myself that I am into becoming an entrepreneur and not just an instructor. Living my life, I desire wholeheartedly to extend my knowledge and enthusiasm to pursue and master my course/degree which is Business Administration major in Human Resource Management.

Through grabbing this opportunity, I can gain new insights, knowledge, lessons to live by and a wonderful experience as I take these new learning that would really help me become a healthy, happy, successful and a delightful entrepreneur. One thing that I am certain for now is to have then a vertical alignment and articulation of my personal and professional life. As Benjamin Franklin concludes and I quote, "*an investment of college education always pays the best interests.*" That is *my life, my living*.